



Study Certificate

This is to certify that Mr. Samiullah Khan

Gender: Male

Nationality: Pakistani

Passport No: VV4132831

Date of Birth: 01/04/1994

Is now a full-time PhD student in English taught program of Electrical Engineering in Taiyuan University of Technology under A- category scholarship with 2500RMB monthly Stipend.

Duration from Sep. 2020 to July 2023.

College of international Education Exchange

Taiyuan university of Technology

March 30, 2021

国际教育交流学院